

THE EFFECT OF PHENYL GROUP ON THE ROTATORY POWER : PHENYLCAMPHORANILIC ACIDS AND *p*-IMINO-*d*-CAMPHORDIPHENYL.

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2', 3' and 4'-phenylcamphoranilic acids and *p*-imino-*d*-camphordiphenyl have been prepared and the rotatory powers observed at the full neutralisation point.

It is now well established that the polar effect of a substituent group is manifest in optical activity. The order in which the substituents are arranged is identical with the order obtained from the dipole moment and the dissociation constant of the acid (Rule, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1121, and subsequent papers). The electron attractive or electron repulsive nature of groups is identified with the amount of restraint exercised by the groups over their co-valency electrons and the common substituents give the following diminished order : COOH, NO₂, Halogens, OH, C₆H₅, H, alkyl.

Singh and Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 486) have, however, shown that the position of the CN group in the sequence of substituent groups is anomalous. We have now prepared phenylcamphoranilic acids. 4'-Phenylcamphoranilic acid has $[\alpha]_D = 64^\circ$ which is next to 4'-carboxylcamphoranilic acid in the series which represent a gradual transition from strongly electronegative groups through hydrogen to those increasingly electropositive in character. The values of the 4'-acids in methyl alcohol are given below.

COOH	Ph	Et	Cl	CN	OEt	Me	OMe	Br	I
255	64	59	58.8	58	56.3	56	53.3	51.3	48

The phenyl group, which falls after the carboxyl, should be down below the series.

The effect of phenyl group in the 3' position is equally curious and is not easy to explain. The values of the 3'-acids in methyl alcohol are tabulated below.

COOH	Cl	F	OEt	OMe	CN	Br	NO ₂	I	Ph
146	52.5	52.4	50	49.7	48.4	44.3	43.2	41.69	40.8

It was expected that the phenyl group would be high up in the series, but it occupies the extreme end position. In methylethyl ketone, 3'-phenyl-

camphoranilic acid gives negative rotation $[\alpha]_D = -7.5^\circ$, a behaviour hitherto not shown by any other group in the *meta* position.

The behaviour of the phenyl group is, however, quite normal in the 2' position. It gives low rotation in methyl and ethyl alcohols and acetone and the sign is reversed in methyl ethyl ketone.

Rupe and Wolfsleben (*Annalen*, 1912, 395, 135) have studied the effect of the phenyl group on rotatory power. They also have come to the conclusion that close to the asymmetric C-atom the phenyl group nearly always increases the optical rotation, but in general its effect is curious.

The rotatory powers of all the three acids were determined at the full neutralisation point and in every case there is an increase (*vide experimental*).

We have also prepared *p*-imino-*d*-camphordiphenyl by condensing camphorquinone with *p*-aminodiphenyl and have determined its rotatory powers in various solvents. These values and those of phenyliminocamphor are given below.

	MeOH	EtOH	C ₆ H ₆	CHCl ₃	C ₂ H ₅ N
<i>p</i> -Imino- <i>d</i> -camphorphenyl	606.8	...	...	726.0	...
<i>p</i> -Imino- <i>d</i> -camphordiphenyl	696.8	720.7	775	780	782

There is thus a small increase in the rotatory power by the introduction of the phenyl group. It was, however, expected that with the length of the conjugated system, the increase would be much greater. The formulae of the two are given for the sake of comparison.

p-Imino-*d*-camphorphenyl

p-Imino-*d*-camphordiphenyl

p-Imino-*d*-camphordiphenyl was reduced by shaking the ethereal solution with zinc and 10% potassium hydroxide. Diphenylaminocamphor crystallised as white leaf crystals, $[\alpha]_D = 82.3^\circ$ (ethyl alcohol). This was expected as the conjugation is broken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Camphoric anhydride and aminodiphenyls in molecular proportions were heated with a little fused sodium acetate for 3 to 4 hours in an oil-bath at 130-135° in the case of *para* and at 120° in the case of *ortho* and *meta*. The product was extracted with dilute ammonium hydroxide solution and

the filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid mass was crystallised from alcohol (animal charcoal).

2'-Phenylcamphoranilic acid crystallised from alcohol as white crystalline product, m.p. 181°. It is readily soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and methylethyl ketone. (Found: N, 4.27; equiv., 351. $C_{22}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 3.98 per cent. equiv., 351).

3'-Phenylcamphoranilic acid was obtained as crystalline powder with a faint pinkish tinge, m.p. 204-5°. (Found: N, 4.18; equiv., 349. $C_{22}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 3.98 per cent. equiv., 351).

4'-Phenylcamphoranilic acid was obtained as white amorphous powder, m.p. 196-97° after shrinking at 194°. (Found: N, 4.17; equiv., 353. $C_{22}H_{25}O_3N$ requires N, 3.98 per cent. equiv., 351).

Equimolecular quantities of *p*-aminodiphenyl and camphorquinone with anhydrous sodium sulphate as a condensing agent, were heated for 3 hours on a water-bath. After cooling, the condensed product was poured into water. The dark brown colouring matter was removed after repeated crystallisations from dilute alcohol and treatment with animal charcoal whereby beautiful yellow crystals were obtained, m.p. 148-49°. (Found: N, 4.4. $C_{22}H_{25}ON$ requires N, 4.4 per cent). It is readily soluble in common organic solvents.

TABLE I.

Rotation of phenylcamphoranilic acids.

Solvent.	2'-Phenyl acid.		3'-Phenyl acid.		4'-Phenyl acid.	
	Conc. (g./25 c.c.)	α_D^{20} [α] _D ²⁰ .	Conc. (g./25 c.c.)	α_D^{20} [α] _D ²⁰ .	Conc. (g./25 c.c.)	α_D^{20} [α] _D ²⁰ .
MeOH	0.2500	0.53 26.5	0.1500	0.49 40.8	0.2500	1.28 64.0
EtOH	0.2500	0.46 23.0	0.1500	0.30 25.0	0.2500	1.10 55.0
Me ₂ CO	0.2500	0.14 7.0	0.1500	0.23 19.6	...	...
MeEtCO	0.2500	-0.12 -6.0	0.1500	-0.09 -7.5	...	...
CHCl ₃	...	...	...	...	0.1500	0.51 42.5
After full neutralisation with						
NaOH	0.1755	0.50 35.6	0.2500	1.10 55.0	0.1755	1.05 74.7

TABLE II.

<i>p</i> -Imino- <i>d</i> -camphordiphenyl.					
Conc. (g./25 c.c.) = 0.1200					
Solvents.	n_D	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	Solvents.	n_D	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$
EtOH	6.92	720.7	MeEtCO	6.83	711.4
MeOH	6.69	696.8	Benzene	7.44	775.0
Me ₂ CO	6.75	703.1	CHCl ₃	7.49	780.2
			Pyridine	7.51	782.1
<i>p</i> -Amino- <i>d</i> -camphordiphenyl.					
Conc. (g./25 c.c.) = 0.1200					
Solvents.	n_D	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$			
EtOH	7.79	82.3			
MeEtCO	7.89	92.7			
C ₆ H ₆	7.96	100.0			

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